

Electrode kinetics of Zn^{II} complexes with Erythromycin at D.M.E.

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Abstract : The electrochemical reduction of Zn^{II} with microlide antibiotic drug, Erythromycin at D.M.E. has been reported for the first time. The electrode reduction in the system is found to be irreversible and diffusion controlled, hence kinetic parameters (K^o_{fn} , αn) have been calculated and reported. System has also been studied in different aqueous - non aqueous solvent mixtures and also at different temperatures.

Keywords : Erythromycin, Zn^{II}, polarography, kinetic parameters.

Introduction

Erythromycin is a microlide antibiotic drug for respiratory tract infection and it has better coverage of a typical organism, including mycoplasma. It is also used to treat outbreak of chlamydia, syphilis and gonorrhoea. It also prevents bacteria from growing, by interfering with their protein synthesis. Here in the present paper, attempts have been made to study electrochemical behavior of complexes of Zn^{II} with Erythromycin via direct current polarography. Earlier, studies of clarithromycin, erythromycin and roxithromycin with essential and trace elements have been done by Sabri Rizwana. Spectroscopic and polarographic techniques have also been used to study copper(II)-azithromycin interactions under equilibrium conditions¹. Polarographic studies of the complexes of zinc with various amino acids²⁻⁴ and antibiotics⁵ have already been reported. Here in the present communication, in view of irreversible nature of reduction wave, kinetic parameters (K^o_{fn} , αn) have been calculated employing Meites-Israel⁶ and Gaur-Bhargava⁷ methods. Kinetic parameters for complexes of metals such as Zn, In, Cd and Pd have also been reported previously⁸⁻¹².

Results and discussion

Single and well defined polarograms were obtained for complexes of Zn^{II} with Erythromycin in the concentration range 0.27×10^{-4} to 2.45×10^{-4} in 20% metha-

nol and 20% ethanol at 25 °C and 30 °C. With the increasing concentration of Erythromycin, shift in half wave potential towards more negative side and the decrease in diffusion current, confirms the complex formation. The plots of $\log [i/(i_d - i)]$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ (Fig. 2) were linear with higher slope values suggesting electrode reaction to be irreversible. The direct proportionality of the diffusion

Fig. 1. Effect of increasing concentration on i_d of Zn. Series 1 = Polarogram of pure metal $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, Series 2 = Polarogram of metal and drug $2.7 \times 10^{-5} M$, Series 3 = Polarogram of metal and drug $1.09 \times 10^{-4} M$, Series 4 = Polarogram of metal and drug $1.36 \times 10^{-4} M$, Series 5 = Polarogram of metal and drug $1.9 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Fig. 2. Graph between $\log i/(i_d - i)$ and voltage of complexation of Erythromycin ($2.7 \times 10^{-5} M$) and zinc ($2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$) at D.M.E. (Similar patterns will be obtained, with different concentrations of Erythromycin, having different slope values).

current to the square root of the height of mercury column indicates that reduction was entirely diffusion controlled. As the complexation of Zn^{II} with Erythromycin is irreversible, hence kinetic parameters like forward rate constant K_{fh}^o and transfer coefficient (αn) have been evaluated using Meites-Israel and Gaur-Bhargava's methods. Polarographic and kinetic parameters are reported in Tables 1 to 4 under different experimental conditions.

From the values reported in Tables 1 to 4, it is observed that values of D decrease with increase in the concentration of complexing agent (Erythromycin). Further, values of K_{fh}^o i.e. formal forward rate constant, calculated by Meites-Israel method and Gaur-Bhargava method, increase with increasing concentration of complexing agent which indicates decrease of irreversibility or increase of reversibility. At higher tempera-

Table 1. Effect of ligand concentration on the polarogram of Zn^{II} ion

$[Zn^{2+}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, Medium = 20% methanol, Temp. = 25 °C, Triton-X-100 = 0.001%

Conc. of Erythromycin (M)	$E_{1/2}$ (V) vs S.C.E.	Slope (mV)	αn (V)	$D \times 10^4$ ($cm^2 s^{-1}$)	K_{fh}^o (M.I.) ($cm s^{-1}$)	K_{fh}^o (G.B.) ($cm s^{-1}$)
0.27×10^{-4}	1.025	55	0.9854	263.9780	5.2191×10^{-15}	7.9414×10^{-15}
0.54×10^{-4}	1.050	59	0.9186	60.5641	1.4750×10^{-14}	2.2443×10^{-14}
0.81×10^{-4}	1.070	62	0.8741	25.5196	2.4750×10^{-14}	4.5877×10^{-14}
1.09×10^{-4}	1.085	65	0.8338	13.5888	7.1978×10^{-14}	1.0952×10^{-13}
1.36×10^{-4}	1.095	67	0.8089	8.3775	1.1811×10^{-13}	1.7975×10^{-13}
1.63×10^{-4}	1.105	68	0.7855	5.6003	1.9301×10^{-13}	2.9369×10^{-13}
1.90×10^{-4}	1.118	71	0.7633	3.6077	3.3258×10^{-13}	5.0605×10^{-13}
2.18×10^{-4}	1.120	72	0.7527	2.9711	3.7162×10^{-13}	5.6545×10^{-13}
2.45×10^{-4}	1.125	73	0.7424	2.3012	4.4353×10^{-13}	6.7494×10^{-13}

Table 2. Effect of ligand concentration on the polarogram of Zn^{II} ion

$[Zn^{2+}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, Medium = 20% methanol, Temp. = 30 °C, Triton-X-100 = 0.001%

Conc. of Erythromycin (M)	$E_{1/2}$ (V) vs S.C.E.	Slope (mV)	αn (V)	$D \times 10^4$ ($cm^2 s^{-1}$)	K_{fh}^o (M.I.) ($cm s^{-1}$)	K_{fh}^o (G.B.) ($cm s^{-1}$)
0.27×10^{-4}	1.035	59	0.9186	305.4175	5.6558×10^{-14}	8.6055×10^{-14}
0.54×10^{-4}	1.060	63	0.8603	69.3639	1.2250×10^{-13}	1.8657×10^{-13}
0.81×10^{-4}	1.085	66	0.7970	29.3308	1.8009×10^{-13}	2.7403×10^{-13}
1.09×10^{-4}	1.105	68	0.7742	15.4079	1.9467×10^{-13}	2.9621×10^{-13}
1.36×10^{-4}	1.120	70	0.7742	9.3531	2.5798×10^{-13}	3.4255×10^{-13}
1.63×10^{-4}	1.134	72	0.7527	6.1518	3.5473×10^{-13}	5.3975×10^{-13}
1.90×10^{-4}	1.146	74	0.7324	4.3555	5.1963×10^{-13}	7.9067×10^{-13}
2.18×10^{-4}	1.158	76	0.7131	3.2109	7.5665×10^{-13}	1.1510×10^{-12}
2.45×10^{-4}	1.165	77	0.7038	2.4891	8.3640×10^{-13}	2.3813×10^{-12}

tures, values of K_{fh}^0 increase and values of αn decrease. A decrease in the values of αn implies that at higher temperature availability of electrons decreases. There is increase in K_{fh}^0 value with increases in temperature, so it shows irreversibility is more at lower temperature and hence product is more stable at lower temperature than at higher temperature. It is observed that the values of K_{fh}^0 are more in 20% ethanol in comparison to 20% methanol. It suggests that system is more irreversible in 20% methanol. It may be due to the physical properties of solvents like viscosity and dielectric constant. The values of kinetic parameter change with change of solvent. In ethanol value of αn and D is less than in methanol. This may due to solvation effect. The viscosity of methanol is more than ethanol. The value of K_{fh}^0 is more in ethanol than methanol. It indicates that system is more irreversible in methanol i.e. products are more stable in methanol in comparison to ethanol.

Applying Lingan's method the value of co-ordination number comes out to be 2 so stoichiometry of complex is 1 : 2 for Zn-Erythromycin complex. The proposed structure is given below :

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade purity (Merck). Their solutions were prepared in triple distilled water. Erythromycin obtained from a local pharmaceutical company, Exim Pharm Int., Mumbai, Maharashtra, India. Solutions of drug had been prepared in distilled ethanol and distilled methanol. To keep the temperature constant thermostat was used. The depolarizer (metal) and ligand (drug) were taken in a definite ratio. The concentration of drug was varied from 0.27×10^{-4} to 2.45×10^{-4} M.

The C-V data for test solutions were recorded after passing pure nitrogen gas in test solution, and 0.001% Triton-X-100 was used as maxima suppressor. A digital Elico D.C. polarograph CL 357 was used to record the current voltage data. This equipment has the three electrode assembly, dropping mercury electrode, calomel as reference electrode and platinum electrode as counter electrode. Dropping mercury electrode had the characteristics $m = 2.422$ mg/s, $t = 3.5$ s and $h = 60$ cm kinetic parameters like forward rate constant K_{fh}^0 and transfer coefficient (αn) have been evaluated using Meites-Israel and Gaur-Bhargava's methods. Polarographic and kinetic

Table 3. Effect of ligand concentration on the polarogram of Zn^{II} ion
 [Zn²⁺] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ M, Medium = 20% ethanol, Temp. = 25 °C, Triton-X-100 = 0.001 %

Conc. of Erythromycin (M)	E _{1/2} (V) vs S.C.E.	Slope (mV)	αn (V)	D × 10 ⁴ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	K ^o _{fh} (M.I.) (cm s ⁻¹)	K ^o _{fh} (G.B.) (cm s ⁻¹)
0.27 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.027	58	0.9344	250.8359	3.6332 × 10 ⁻¹⁴	5.2584 × 10 ⁻¹⁴
0.54 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.052	63	0.8603	57.4852	1.4591 × 10 ⁻¹³	2.2202 × 10 ⁻¹³
0.81 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.072	66	0.8212	24.1641	2.4774 × 10 ⁻¹³	3.7696 × 10 ⁻¹³
1.09 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.083	69	0.7855	12.8443	5.7305 × 10 ⁻¹³	8.7196 × 10 ⁻¹³
1.36 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.093	71	0.7633	7.7573	8.4391 × 10 ⁻¹³	1.2841 × 10 ⁻¹²
1.63 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.100	73	0.7424	5.1779	1.3322 × 10 ⁻¹²	2.0272 × 10 ⁻¹²
1.90 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.108	74	0.7324	3.6534	1.4073 × 10 ⁻¹²	2.1414 × 10 ⁻¹²
2.18 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.113	75	0.7226	2.6840	1.5992 × 10 ⁻¹²	2.4344 × 10 ⁻¹²
2.45 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.117	76	0.7131	2.0767	1.9010 × 10 ⁻¹²	2.8926 × 10 ⁻¹²

Table 4. Effect of ligand concentration on the polarogram of Zn^{II} ion
 [Zn²⁺] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ M, Medium = 20% ethanol, Temp. = 30 °C, Triton-X-100 = 0.001 %

Conc. of Erythromycin (M)	E _{1/2} (V) vs S.C.E.	Slope (mV)	αn (V)	D × 10 ⁴ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	K ^o _{fh} (M.I.) (cm s ⁻¹)	K ^o _{fh} (G.B.) (cm s ⁻¹)
0.27 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.037	63	0.8603	309.9923	5.6027 × 10 ⁻¹³	8.5251 × 10 ⁻¹³
0.54 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.062	68	0.7970	67.1072	1.5473 × 10 ⁻¹²	2.3545 × 10 ⁻¹²
0.81 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.082	71	0.7633	28.3524	2.2382 × 10 ⁻¹²	3.4056 × 10 ⁻¹²
1.09 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.100	74	0.7324	15.1406	3.5990 × 10 ⁻¹²	5.4764 × 10 ⁻¹²
1.36 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.114	76	0.7131	9.1875	4.3460 × 10 ⁻¹²	6.6130 × 10 ⁻¹²
1.63 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.125	78	0.6948	6.1518	5.8438 × 10 ⁻¹²	8.8920 × 10 ⁻¹²
1.90 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.135	80	0.6775	4.3555	8.0593 × 10 ⁻¹²	1.2263 × 10 ⁻¹¹
2.18 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.144	82	0.6609	3.2724	1.1545 × 10 ⁻¹¹	1.7567 × 10 ⁻¹¹
2.45 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.151	83	0.6530	2.3802	1.2097 × 10 ⁻¹¹	1.8407 × 10 ⁻¹¹

parameters are reported in Tables 1 to 4 under different experimental conditions.

Meites-Israel modification of Kotecky's method :

$$E_{d.e.} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)} \quad (1)$$

$$E_{1/2} = \frac{0.0591}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K^o_{fh} t_{1/2}}{D^{1/2}} \quad (2)$$

Gaur-Bhargava modification :

$$E_{d.e.} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)} \quad (3)$$

$$E_{1/2} = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{K^o_{fh} t_{1/2}}{(\text{antilog } C) D^{1/2}} \quad (4)$$

where, K^o_{fh} = formal rate constant for forward reaction,

D = diffusion coefficient, αn = transfer coefficient.

E_{d.e.} and E_{1/2} were determined with respect to calomel electrode. The values of αn were obtained by eq. (1) (Meites-Israel method) and eq. (3) (Gaur-Bhargava method). The values of K^o_{fh} determined by eq. (2) (Meites-Israel method) and eq. (4) (Gaur-Bhargava method). The values of diffusion coefficient (D) were determined using Ilkovic equation.

$$i_d = 607 n D^{1/2} C m^{2/3} t^{1/6} \quad (5)$$

all symbols have their usual meanings.

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